

The Impact of Mode of Drug Administration on Health Care Costs

Authors: *Anna-Katharina Böhm, Tom Stargardt, and Udo Schneider*

ABSTRACT

Objectives: Fixed dose combinations (FDC) are drugs that contain multiple active components in a single dosage form. They facilitate drug use through a simpler medication regimen and thus increase medication adherence. However, they lack flexibility in individual dose titration, may increase the risk of adverse events and enhance polypharmacy. Little is known about their effect on economic outcomes. While an increase in medication adherence may raise pharmaceutical spending, costs may be offset by improved health outcomes. Also copayments may be affected. Hence, we examine the effect of FDC vs. loose dose combinations (LDC) in the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus on costs in Germany, and investigate potential channels contributing to differences in expenditures.

Methods: This non-experimental, retrospective, population-based cohort study is based on administrative claims data from the Techniker Krankenkasse, Germany's largest sickness fund. We included T2DM patients who have received monotherapy during a 12 months pre-index period and switched in 2014 to either FDC (intervention group) or LDC (control group). Patients were followed up for 36 months. Costs are defined i) from the payer's perspective, and divided into pharmaceutical, inpatient and outpatient spending and ii) as copayments for the patients. In order to remove confounders, a two-step risk adjustment was applied: We first used entropy balancing controlling for socio-demographic variables, comorbidities and prescription drug groups to eliminate differences in observable characteristics. Second, we applied Difference-in-Difference estimators for each outcome to account for potential time-invariant unobservable heterogeneity. Subsequently, we compared the expenditure between both groups. In order to analyze channels through which FDCs and LDCs may impact expenditure, we calculate adherence as the proportion of days covered, health care resource utilization in terms of physician visits and hospitalizations, as well as disease-specific comorbidities.

Results: 1307 individuals were included into the analysis of which 805 belong to the FDC and 502 to the LDC cohort. In both cohorts, a combination of metformin plus sitagliptin was the preferred antidiabetic dual combination. Entropy balancing created highly balanced distribution of baseline characteristics between groups. Preliminary regression results suggest no significant differences in total pharmaceutical spending, but higher T2DM-related pharmaceutical costs for the FDC group ($p < 0.01$). Copayments for patients are lower if treated with a single-pill combination ($p < 0.01$). No significant differences in inpatient and outpatient costs were found between both groups.

Discussion: Preliminary results suggest an increase in diabetes-related pharmaceutical costs if treated with FDC. One explanation may be a higher medication possession through increased medication adherence, or the patent status of the innovative drug. Lower copayments of FDCs may be explained by their single package advantage. No significant differences were found in inpatient and outpatient costs, potentially indicating similar health effects of both administration forms. Further analyses are needed to show whether results are stable, and to investigate the overall effect on cost. So far, there is no strong evidence for incentivizing the use of FDC or LDC from an economic perspective.